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Research Article

**ANALYSIS OF FREQUENCY OF PULMONARY
MANIFESTATIONS OF IN PATIENTS WITH GASTRO-
ESOPHAGEAL REFLUX DISEASE**Ahmed Ammar Ali¹, Qurat ul ain Ali¹, Tooba Ali¹¹Sheikh Zayed Hospital Rahim Yar Khan.**Article Received:** August 2019**Accepted:** September 2019**Published:** October 2019**Abstract:**

Introduction: Pulmonary manifestations of GERD are attracting increasing attention. The physiological link between GERD and pulmonary disease has been extensively studied in chronic cough and asthma. The gastric contents can cause throat irritation, postnasal drip and hoarseness also recurrent cough.

Objectives: This study is to determine frequency of pulmonary manifestations in patients with gastroesophageal reflux disease.

Settings: This cross sectional study was conducted in Sheikh Zayed Hospital Rahim Yar Khan during February 2019 to July 2019.

Subjects: All patients with heartburn .both males and females of 20 -70 years of age.

Results: Out of 150 patients laryngeal symptoms were 10 % have dry cough 8 % have hoarseness and dry cough hoarseness both in 10 % in patients with heartburn . 34% patients with GERD were found to be asthmatic. Nasal symptoms were infrequent 2%. Out of 150 patients 36% do not have any pulmonary manifestations.

Conclusion: There is high prevalence of pulmonary manifestations in patients with GERD.

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INTRODUCTION:

Gastroesophageal reflux disease is defined as a condition which occur when the reflux of stomach cause troublesome symptoms [1]. It is a common disorder worldwide [2]. It usually runs a chronic course as individuals ignore it mostly until complications appear. [3] History is simplest and quickest method to diagnose GERD. The diagnosis is important to consider, however, because significant improvement in symptoms and in asthma control occur with appropriately treated GERD [4]. Frequency pulmonary manifestations is very high in patients with GERD [5] and is potential trigger for Asthma and COPD [6].

The objective of this study was to determine frequency of pulmonary manifestation in patients with gastroesophageal reflux disease. The respiratory manifestations seen in patients with GERD are laryngeal, nasal sensual pharyngeal symptoms. Most common manifestations are recurrent cough, hoarseness, chest congestion and lung inflammation leading to asthma, bronchitis shortness of breath and pneumonia. No Data available for nasal symptoms in patients with GERD. These manifestations are may be due to: Direct or vagally mediated irritation of larynx, pharynx and posterior nasal mucosa by gastric contents during reflux [7].

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY:

This cross sectional study was conducted in Sheikh Zayed Hospital Rahim Yar Khan during February 2019 to July 2019. This study included both males and females of 20-70 years old. Patients included were with chronic heart burn and GERD not treated at the time of evaluation. Patients excluded were:

1. COPD/ smokers.
2. Pregnancy.
3. Restrictive pulmonary disease.
4. Pulmonary malignancies or laryngeal stenosis.

Apparatus used was a Questionnaire. Study design was "Cross sectional study". This study was conducted in medical OPD and Emergency of Services Hospital Lahore.

RESULTS:

Out of 150 patients Laryngeal symptoms were 10 % have dry cough 8 % have hoarseness and dry cough hoarseness both in 10 % in patients with heartburn . 34% patients with GERD were found to be asthmatic. Nasal symptoms were infrequent 2%. Out of 150 patients 36% do not have any pulmonary manifestation.

Following table and bar chart shows that 64% patients with GERD have pulmonary manifestations and 36% have no pulmonary manifestations.

Pulmonary manifestations in GERD	
Symptoms	%age of patients
Present	64%
Absent	36%

Following table shows Age distribution of pulmonary manifestations in patients of GERD Younger age groups most commonly affected.

Pulmonary manifestations	Number of patients with GERD (years)					Total no of patients included in study	
	Age	20-30	31-40	41-50	51-60		61-70
Dry cough		07	02	03	02	01	15
Hoarseness		05	02	03	01	01	12
Both dry cough and hoarseness		08	02	03	02	00	15
Asthma		27	07	08	05	04	51
Nasal symptoms		02	01	00	00	00	03
No pulmonary manifestations		-	-	-	-	-	54
							150

DISCUSSION:

A causal relationship between asthma and GERD has been known and researched upon for some time now. GERD is considered to be the third leading cause of

chronic cough and affects an estimated 20% of the patients. [12-13] Different mechanisms of esophageal acid-induced bronchoconstriction include a vagal-reflex, local axonal reflexes, bronchial hyper-

reactivity, and microaspiration. Asthmatics are predisposed to GERD development because of a high prevalence of hiatal hernia, autonomic dysfunction and an increased pressure gradient between the abdominal and thoracic cavity: Literature review showed that GERD in patients with chronic sinusitis, laryngitis, and pharyngitis and support the consideration of GERD in patients with upper airway symptoms recalcitrant to treatment [14-17]. These investigators postulated a causal relationship between GERD and pulmonary manifestations of GERD [14-16]. Support of this hypothesis requires the demonstration of an increased prevalence of pulmonary manifestations in a population of patients with GERD. The subjects of the present study were selected on the basis of their chronic heartburn and not upper airway pathology. Collection of the questionnaire answers was completed without the subjects being aware that the association of pulmonary manifestations with GERD was being studied.

CONCLUSION:

There is high prevalence of pulmonary manifestations in patients with GERD.

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